

ANALYZING OPERATIONAL AND MAINTENANCE STRATEGIES FOR ELECTROLYSIS-BASED HYDROGEN PRODUCTION FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogen (H₂) is recognized as a key enabler of decarbonization in energy-intensive industries. However, the economic viability of H₂ production via renewable-powered electrolysis remains a major challenge. While advancements in electrolyzer technology are essential, further cost reductions can be achieved through optimized operational and maintenance (O&M) strategies. This study develops an agent-based simulation model to represent an electrolysis-based H₂ production system over its lifetime and evaluate the impact of alternative O&M strategies on economic performance, degradation dynamics, and H₂ demand fulfillment. The electrolyzer uses wind power and is supported by grid electricity, while the model explicitly captures startups, load-dependent efficiency, degradation effects, and stack replacement actions. Results show that operational constraints have a marginal impact on long-term performance, with limited gains in cost and stack lifetime from avoiding inefficient low-load operation. In contrast, carefully defined stack replacement policies lead to substantially larger lifetime cost reductions, up to 21% compared to overly conservative replacement strategies. The findings further highlight multiple trade-offs associated with selecting the replacement threshold, as well as the robustness of condition-based stack replacement under degradation uncertainty.

INTRODUCTION

H₂ has the potential to support industrial decarbonization, particularly in sectors that are difficult to electrify due to high-temperature heat requirements and reliance on fossil fuel combustion, such as glass, aluminum, and steel manufacturing (Trapani et al., 2025). However, about 60% of global H₂ production still relies on natural gas without carbon capture (IEA, 2025), and its use in industrial applications can offset decarbonization benefits and even increase overall emissions compared to

current levels (Fede et al., 2025). Nevertheless, H₂ production via renewable-powered electrolysis is not yet cost-competitive (IEA, 2025) and improving its economic viability requires leveraging all available cost-reduction opportunities. While capital expenditure represents a major share of total H₂ production costs, further savings can come from electrolyzers operation and maintenance over their lifetime (Bak et al., 2025; Arnold et al., 2025). Stack degradation is of particular importance, as the stack component of the electrolyzer system accounts for up to 45% of the total investment (IRENA, 2020). Therefore, identifying operational strategies, such as minimum operating load constraints, that mitigate degradation and extend stack lifetime, alongside maintenance strategies to manage stack replacements, becomes essential for improving the economic performance of electrolysis-based H₂ production and contributing to the overall economic viability of the transition (Arnold et al., 2025).

In line with these motivations, this study investigates the impact of alternative O&M strategies on economic performance, stack degradation dynamics and demand fulfillment in electrolysis-based H₂ production systems using an agent-based simulation model to capture the system's behavior over its lifetime.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. First, the relevant literature is reviewed, highlighting the research gaps this study seeks to address. Next, the agent-based simulation model is presented, outlining the agents, the control strategy, and the O&M strategies. The case study assumptions and tested scenarios are then presented, followed by the analysis and discussion of the results. Finally, the paper concludes with the main findings, limitations, and directions for future research.

RELATED WORK

Relevant research on O&M strategies for electrolysis-based H₂ production can be grouped into two main streams. The first focuses on operational strategies to improve economic performance. For example, Bak et al. (2025) analyze alternative operational strategies, including limiting startups, while jointly optimizing system design. Their results show that higher minimum

operating loads increase costs, whereas a minimum “on” time of 6 hours reduces both costs and startups. However, the study neglects degradation effects and addresses only variations in system sizing.

The second stream focuses on stack replacement strategies to enhance economic performance. Park et al. (2025) examine different degradation modelling approaches and efficiency-based replacement thresholds. Their findings indicate that omitting startup-induced degradation underestimates degradation, leading to longer replacement intervals and an overestimation of economic performance. Furthermore, intermediate thresholds (14-21% efficiency reduction) minimize costs by extending stack lifetime and reducing replacement frequency. However, their analysis does not differentiate between the degradation effects of hot and cold startups. Arnold et al. (2025) determine the cost-optimal stack replacement period under different degradation rates and load-dependent degradation mechanisms. Their analysis reveals that degradation rate assumptions have the greatest influence on outcomes and identifies an optimal replacement period of 7 years (20% degradation threshold) in the baseline case. Nevertheless, startup-induced degradation is not considered in their evaluation. Campbell-Stanway et al. (2025) analyze both time-based and condition-based stack replacement thresholds, concluding that condition-based replacement does not provide a significant advantage over time-based strategies. However, the impact of variability in degradation assumptions on the effectiveness of these strategies is not investigated.

Unlike previous research, this study adopts an integrated perspective on O&M strategies for electrolysis-based H₂ production. It evaluates not only the economic impact of O&M decisions, as is common in the literature, but also examines how operational strategies influence degradation dynamics and stack lifetime, and how stack replacement thresholds affect the system’s ability to meet H₂ demand. Furthermore, the study assesses how economic parameters affect the effectiveness of operational constraints. Finally, the distinct degradation contributions of hot and cold startups are explicitly incorporated, and the impact of uncertainty in both operation- and startup-driven degradation rates on economic performance and the robustness of the maintenance strategies is evaluated.

Figure 1. Main System Components

SIMULATION MODEL

This paper employs an agent-based simulation model to represent the electrolysis-based H₂ production system, as illustrated in Figure 1, and to evaluate its performance under different O&M strategies. This approach is adopted as it enables modelling each system component, namely the wind power source, electrical grid, electrolyzer, H₂ storage, and combustion unit, as an agent with distinct characteristics, while capturing their dynamic interactions over an extended time horizon.

Wind Power Source Agent

The wind power source supplies renewable electrical energy for electrolyzer operation. The wind power curve described by Ao et al. (2025) is used to estimate available electrical power, utilizing wind speed data and turbine parameters including rated power, cut-in speed, cut-out speed, and rated speed. The decision variable for this agent is the quantity of wind power consumed by the electrolyzer. An electricity price is applied to calculate the corresponding cost of wind power consumption.

Electrical Grid Agent

The electrical grid provides supplementary electrical power when wind power and H₂ storage are insufficient to meet demand. The decision variable is the amount of grid electricity consumed, and the corresponding cost is calculated using the grid electricity price.

Electrolyzer Agent

The electrolyzer converts electrical power into H₂ via water electrolysis. Its operational behavior is represented by a three-state model comprising production, standby, and idle states (Wang et al., 2024), as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Three-State Model of the Electrolyzer

In the production state, the electrolyzer produces H₂ and consumes power based on the operating load. In the standby state, the system does not produce H₂ but consumes a reduced amount of power. In the idle state, neither H₂ production nor power consumption occurs. Additionally, a hot startup happens when the electrolyzer transitions from standby to production, while a cold startup occurs when transitioning from idle to production. Startup events temporarily delay production and contribute to degradation, whereas shutdowns have a negligible duration and no impact on degradation. The three-state model is implemented using a state-chart within the electrolyzer agent.

In the production state, the H₂ production flow rate H_{2t} (Nm³/h) is estimated as in Equation (1), where P^r denotes the rated power of the electrolyzer (kW), L_t is the operating load, Δt indicates the duration of the time interval (h), η_t refers to the electrolyzer's efficiency, and LHV is the lower heating value of H₂ (kWh/Nm³).

$$H_{2t} = \frac{P^r \cdot L_t \cdot \Delta t \cdot \eta_t}{LHV} \quad (1)$$

The electrolyzer efficiency depends on the operating load (Kuang et al., 2024) and decreases due to accumulated voltage degradation ΔV_t (V) (Arnold et al., 2025). This relationship is illustrated in Figure 3 and expressed by Equation (2), where $\eta_0(L_t)$ denotes the efficiency of a non-degraded electrolyzer at operating load L_t , and α is a conversion coefficient primarily based on the molar mass of H₂ and the Faraday constant.

$$\eta_t = \frac{\eta_0(L_t)}{1 + \eta_0(L_t) \cdot \frac{\alpha \Delta V_t}{LHV}} \quad (2)$$

Accumulated voltage degradation is estimated using Equation (3), where ΔV^p , ΔV^{hs} , and ΔV^{cs} represent the voltage degradation contributions from operating intervals, hot startups, and cold startups, respectively. N_t^p , N_t^{hs} , and N_t^{cs} indicate the cumulative number of operating intervals, hot startups, and cold startups since the most recent stack replacement.

$$\Delta V_t = \Delta V^p \cdot N_t^p + \Delta V^{hs} \cdot N_t^{hs} + \Delta V^{cs} \cdot N_t^{cs} \quad (3)$$

Stack replacement is modelled as a dedicated state in the electrolyzer state-chart. The system transitions to this maintenance state from any operational state once the stack replacement condition is triggered. After maintenance is completed, the system returns to the idle state, and all cumulative degradation counters are reset. Additional variables included in the electrolyzer agent are water consumption, associated with a unit cost, and the total number of stack replacements performed.

Figure 3. Electrolyzer Efficiency based on Operating Load and Accumulated Voltage Degradation

Hydrogen Storage Agent

The H₂ storage acts as a buffer, storing surplus H₂ produced during periods of high wind power availability and supplying it during periods of low availability. The

storage dynamics are modelled using conventional inventory balance equations, where the inventory level at each time interval is determined by the previous level and the current inflows and outflows. The key variable is the H₂ inventory level, which directly determines H₂ inventory holding costs. A safety stock level and a maximum storage capacity are introduced.

Combustion Agent

Lastly, the combustion process is the end-use application, requiring a specified H₂ demand to cover the high-temperature heat needs. If the available H₂ supply is insufficient, the remaining unmet demand is quantified.

Control Strategy

To simulate the system's behavior, a control strategy is designed to prioritize wind power utilization and H₂ storage before resorting to grid electricity (adapted from Trapani et al., 2025).

- If wind power is available and sufficient to meet the electrolyzer's minimum operating load, the electrolyzer produces H₂ using wind power.
- If H₂ production from wind power exceeds the demand and storage capacity is available, the excess H₂ is stored.
- If H₂ production from wind power is insufficient to meet demand, the shortfall is partially or fully met by withdrawing H₂ from storage and, if necessary, by supplementing the electrolyzer's power input with electricity from the grid.
- If wind power is available but insufficient to meet the electrolyzer's minimum operating load, the electrolyzer is either placed on standby (if wind power can cover standby consumption) or set to idle when the stored H₂ is sufficient to meet demand while maintaining the safety stock level; otherwise, grid electricity is used to operate the electrolyzer.
- If the electrolyzer is on standby or in the idle state and the H₂ storage level falls below the safety stock threshold, the electrolyzer switches to production regardless of wind power availability.

Operational Strategies

The following operational strategies (Bak et al., 2025) are assessed regarding their effects on economic performance and stack degradation:

- OS1: Minimum operating load
- OS2: Minimum "on" time

OS1 imposes a minimum operating load on the electrolyzer to avoid inefficient operation at very low loads. As shown in Figure 3, the efficiency substantially decreases at reduced load levels, resulting in a higher specific power consumption per unit of H₂ produced.

OS2 enforces a minimum "on" time constraint, requiring the electrolyzer to remain operational for a predefined period upon entering the production state. This restriction aims to limit frequent startups, which are major contributors to stack degradation.

Maintenance Strategies

The following maintenance strategies for stack replacement are evaluated in terms of their impact on production performance and stack degradation:

- MS1: Maximum number of operating hours
- MS2: Maximum voltage degradation

MS1 involves replacing the stack after a predetermined number of operating hours. As a time-based strategy, it is easy to implement; however, it does not consider the actual stack degradation level, potentially leading to premature or delayed replacement.

MS2 requires stack replacement when accumulated voltage degradation reaches a predefined threshold. This condition-based strategy ensures stack utilization up to a specified degradation level, but it necessitates continuous monitoring of degradation indicators.

CASE STUDY AND SIMULATION SCENARIOS

The simulation model is implemented in AnyLogic 8.9 and run over a 30-year horizon, with one-minute resolution to capture hot and cold startup durations. The case study considers a glass manufacturing company located in France with an estimated stable H₂ demand of 700 Nm³/h. Historical national-level wind speed and grid electricity price data covering the period 2016-2025 are used as inputs and replicated over the simulation horizon. A 5 MW Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolyzer is modelled to cover the average H₂ demand, with a wind-to-electrolyzer capacity ratio of 2.8 (Marocco et al., 2024). Regarding electrolyzer stack degradation, the voltage degradation contributions per operating interval, hot startup, and cold startup are assumed to be $8 \cdot 10^{-8}$ V/min, $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ V and $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ V, respectively (U.S. Department of Energy, 2022; Fede et al., 2025). Lastly, the system includes a 14,000 Nm³ H₂ storage tank with a safety stock of 700 Nm³ (equivalent to one hour demand coverage).

The baseline scenario assumes a minimum load of 5%, in line with the technical specifications of commercial PEM electrolyzers, no minimum “on” time constraint, and stack replacements performed at 10% voltage degradation, consistent with established guidelines (U.S. Department of Energy, 2022). For each O&M strategy, a range of values is evaluated to assess its impact on system performance (Table 1).

Table 1. Operational and Maintenance Strategies Scenarios Tested

OS1	OS2	MS1	MS2
5-25 %	0-96 h	10,000-100,000 h	2-20 %

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Operational Strategies Results

This section presents and discusses the results obtained from the scenarios analyzed for OS1 and OS2.

Under baseline assumptions, OS1 results show that restricting the minimum operating load reduces operating

cost by less than 0.06% across all scenarios (orange curve in Figure 5). As shown in Figure 4, increasing the minimum load to 12.5% marginally reduces electricity cost by avoiding inefficient operation at low load levels, while further increases raise electricity costs due to reduced operational flexibility, lower wind power utilization, and increased reliance on more expensive grid electricity. Higher minimum loads also reduce inventory costs by decreasing storage levels, creating a trade-off between electricity and inventory costs. Consequently, operating costs are minimized at a minimum operating load of 17.5%.

Figure 4. Impact of Minimum Operating Load on Electricity and H₂ Inventory Costs

Because OS1 aims to minimize inefficient operation and efficiency is directly linked to electricity consumption, the impact of wind electricity price on system performance is examined. This choice is further motivated by electricity accounting for 86% of total operating cost, and wind power representing 62% of the electricity mix.

Figure 5. Impact of Minimum Operating Load and Wind Electricity Cost on Operating Cost Variation

Figure 5 (blue and green curves) illustrates the resulting percentage variation in operating cost relative to a 5% minimum operating load, confirming the limited but positive impact of this operational constraint, with cost reductions of up to 0.08%. The results further indicate that the minimum operating load minimizing cost depends on the wind electricity price, with stricter operational constraints preferred at higher prices due to the reduced cost competitiveness of wind power relative to grid electricity. Overall, a minimum load of 17.5% consistently reduces operating cost.

From a degradation perspective, higher minimum loads increase hot startups while reducing cold startups and operating intervals. Since operating intervals are most frequent and cold startups have the greatest impact on degradation, this results in lower voltage degradation and an extended stack lifetime. A minimum operating load of 17.5% increases stack lifetime by approximately 1.10% and is therefore adopted for subsequent analyses.

Results for OS2 indicate that imposing a minimum “on” time has a negligible impact on economic performance, as the system already operates nearly continuously. Increasing the minimum “on” time significantly lowers the number of startups, particularly hot startups, confirming reduced system cycling and aligning with the motivation behind OS2. However, under baseline degradation assumptions, this does not improve degradation performance. Instead, average voltage degradation slightly increases by 0.03%, as fewer startups are offset by longer continuous operating periods. Given its limited yet adverse impact on both cost and degradation, OS2 is not further analyzed.

In summary, the analysis of operational strategies demonstrates that a moderate increase in the minimum operating load slightly improves economic performance and enhances stack lifetime. In contrast, imposing minimum 'on' time constraints has a marginal negative effect on both economic performance and degradation.

Maintenance Strategies Results

This section analyzes maintenance strategies MS1 and MS2 and their effects on system performance. For MS1, Figure 6 shows that the unit H₂ operating cost (based on total H₂ production over the system lifetime) varies non-monotonically with the number of operating hours before stack replacement, reflecting a trade-off between electricity and inventory costs and the discrete nature of replacement events (indicated by the labels).

Figure 6. Impact of Operating Hours Until Stack Replacement on Unit H₂ Operating Cost. Labels Indicate the Number of Stack Replacements

Replacing the stack before 40,000 hours significantly increases costs, reaching 0.43 €/Nm³ at 10,000 hours. Thresholds between 40,000 and 70,000 hours yield a 15% cost reduction, forming a cost plateau around 0.37 €/Nm³. Beyond 70,000 hours, cost increases by up to 4% due to greater degradation, which lowers electrolyzer efficiency and raises electricity consumption, without significant savings in stack replacement costs.

Within the 40,000-70,000 hour range, comparable economic performance suggests selecting the replacement threshold based on secondary criteria. Lower thresholds reduce accumulated degradation (from 17.7% to 10.1%) and enhance the safety margin, making them appropriate when prioritizing reliability and minimizing the risk of unplanned failures. In contrast, higher thresholds extend stack lifetime (from 4.6 to 8.1 years) and reduce the frequency of maintenance interventions, making them preferable for minimizing planned shutdowns and operational interruptions.

When degradation can be directly measured, stack replacement can be scheduled based on a predefined degradation threshold, as in MS2. Figure 7 presents the associated economic performance. In line with previous results, low thresholds lead to more frequent replacements, which significantly increase costs, reaching 0.46 €/Nm³ at a 2% voltage degradation. At higher thresholds, replacement frequency decreases, and operating costs are reduced by up to 21%, reaching a minimum of approximately 0.36 €/Nm³ at a 14% threshold, which corresponds to an average stack lifetime of 6.4 years. Beyond this threshold, costs rise again as degradation intensifies, leading to higher electricity consumption.

Figure 7. Impact of Voltage Degradation Until Stack Replacement on Unit H₂ Operating Cost. Labels Indicate the Number of Stack Replacements

To account for uncertainty in voltage degradation parameters, a sensitivity analysis is performed at 50% and 200% of baseline values. While variations in degradation from hot and cold startups have a negligible impact on both cost and stack lifetime, degradation during operating intervals has the most significant effect, resulting in up to 13% cost variation.

Figure 8 shows the unit H₂ operating cost across stack replacement thresholds and degradation rates for operating intervals (ΔV^p), for MS1 (Figure 8.a) and MS2 (Figure 8.b). In MS2, the threshold that yields the minimum cost (black marker) remains consistent across scenarios, as the threshold definition is directly linked to degradation. In contrast, for MS1, the cost-minimizing threshold shifts with different degradation assumptions. Therefore, MS2 emerges as a more robust stack replacement strategy under uncertainty in degradation behavior and is further investigated in this study.

Figure 8. Impact of Voltage Degradation Rate During Operating Interval on Unit H₂ Operating Cost under Different Stack Replacement Strategies

Previous analyses assumed negligible stack replacement durations. In practice, replacement entails a significant electrolyzer shutdown, disrupting H₂ production and affecting demand fulfillment. Figure 9 shows the impact of replacement duration on total unmet H₂ demand and service level across different degradation thresholds, where service level is the percentage of total H₂ demand satisfied over the system lifetime. Longer replacement durations reduce system availability, especially at low thresholds, where frequent replacements and associated shutdowns significantly increase unmet demand and lower service levels. Higher thresholds mitigate this effect, with demand fulfillment stabilizing once voltage degradation exceeds approximately 14%. Nevertheless, higher thresholds result in greater accumulated degradation, which may increase the risk of unplanned disruptions, introducing an additional trade-off. Practically, intermediate thresholds offer a compromise by limiting planned downtime while avoiding excessive degradation-related risks.

In summary, the analysis of maintenance strategies demonstrates that very low replacement thresholds significantly worsen both economic performance and demand fulfillment. Intermediate thresholds minimize operating costs, while higher thresholds improve service level. The selection of an appropriate threshold should also consider the trade-off between extending stack lifetime and limiting accumulated degradation to reduce the risk of unplanned shutdowns. Moreover, a condition-based stack replacement policy enhances robustness under uncertainty in degradation dynamics.

Figure 9. Impact of Stack Replacement Duration on Total Unmet H₂ Demand and Service Level

CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the impact of different O&M strategies on the performance of renewable-powered water electrolysis systems for H₂ production. The work contributes to improving H₂ economic viability and supporting its integration into industrial processes for decarbonization. An agent-based simulation model was developed to represent system's behavior under alternative scenarios.

From an operational perspective, avoiding inefficient operation at very low loads marginally improves cost performance (0.06% reduction) by reducing electricity consumption, while also enhancing stack lifetime (1.10% increase). In contrast, imposing a minimum "on" time does not yield economic benefits or mitigate degradation.

The analysis of maintenance strategies shows that stack replacement thresholds significantly influence both cost performance (up to a 21% reduction) and the system's ability to meet demand. Exploring alternative thresholds reveals an inherent trade-off between limiting accumulated degradation and extending stack lifetime. Additionally, a replacement policy based on accumulated degradation provides greater robustness to uncertainty in degradation parameters. Across the scenarios considered, an intermediate voltage degradation threshold of 14% minimizes operating costs without compromising service level while limiting the risks associated with higher accumulated degradation.

Some limitations of this study should be acknowledged, including its application to a specific system configuration, which may limit the generalizability of the results, and the assessment of unmet demand based solely on planned downtimes, without accounting for the increasing risk of failures or unexpected disruptions at higher degradation levels. Building on these findings, future research should investigate optimal stack replacement policies that jointly consider economic performance and more comprehensive assessments of system reliability. In addition, the robustness of the results should be evaluated under varying operating conditions and system sizing configurations, and the findings should be validated using real-world electrolysis-based H₂ systems.

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